

Deliverable D1.1

Project Handbook and Risk Monitoring Framework

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Log of changes

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Table of contents

<i>Log of changes</i>	2
1. Executive Summary	5
2. Contribution towards project objectives	6
3. Project Overview	8
3.1 Basic project information	8
3.2 Short names of the consortium partners	9
3.3 Project Acronyms	11
3.4 Project Summary	12
3.5 Project scope and work structure	13
4. Project management structure	15
4.1 Project governing model	15
4.2 Project coordination and management	15
4.3 Description of roles and responsibilities	16
4.4 Decision-making and advisory bodies	21
4.5 Communications management	26
5. Project Reporting	29
5.1 Deliverables	29
5.2 Milestones	34
5.3 Progress reporting	35
6. Project Processes	37
6.1 Risk management	37
6.2 Issue management	38
6.3 Project change management	39
6.4 Quality management	40
6.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	43
6.6 Data management plan	43

6.7 Internal conflict resolution and escalation	43
7. Configuration management	44
7.1 Storage of project management artefacts	44
7.2 Naming convention of project management artefacts	45
7.3 Versioning of project management artefacts	45
7.4 File Exchange and Repository	46
8. Key legal document	47
8.1 Grant Agreement	47
9. Ethical considerations	50

1. Executive Summary

The Project Handbook provides a complete overview of the management and administrative procedures and principles to ensure an efficient execution of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, thus contributing to the production of high quality project results. It contains all relevant planning information that the consortium partners will use as a framework for delivery during the course of the project, therefore, it is the point of reference for all consortium partners and stakeholders.

The Project Handbook documents the selected approach for implementing the project goals, including the milestones, deliverables and relevant KPIs. It also highlights the key controlling processes to be used, the project policies and rules, and the overall management approach, including, but not limited to management structure, tasks, decision-making procedures, responsibilities and roles. Language adopted throughout the documents aims to be clear and concise.

The Project Handbook is kept up to date throughout the life of the project through annual revisions.

This is a guidance document. It should not be relied upon for making any legal assessments, for which Beneficiaries should always refer to the Grant Agreement (including its annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No

<p>implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)</p>	No
	<p>3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).</p>	No
	<p>4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)</p>	No
	<p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	No
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	No
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p>	No
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	Yes

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	No
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).</p>	No
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).</p>	No
	<p>4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)</p>	No

3. Project Overview

3.1 Basic project information

Project Call	Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem (2023)
Project Title	A European Network of TRUSTed research environments
Project Acronym	EOSC-ENTRUST
Grant Agreement	101131056
Call Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06
Contracting Authority	REA/C/04
Project Start Date	1st March 2024
Project End Date	28th February 2027
Duration	36 months

Lump Sum Contribution Awarded	€ 4 218 809,75
Number of Beneficiaries	24
Number of Affiliated Entities	5
Number of Affiliated Partners	5
Website	https://eosc-entrust.eu/
X	https://twitter.com/eosc_entrust
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-entrust/

3.2 Short names of the consortium partners

Table 1. All Beneficiaries, Affiliated Entities and Associated Partners of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, as of *May 2024*. The updated list will always be accessible via the [Participant's Portal](#) (login required).

Number	Organisation or Institute name	Short name
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	ELIXIR / EMBL-EBI
2	TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	CSC
3	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC
4	EUDAT OY	EUDAT
5	STICHTING HEALTH-RI	HEALTH-RI
6	Masarykova univerzita	MU
7	SIGMA2 AS	SIGMA2
8	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	UiB
8.1	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	NTNU
8.2	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO
9	SURF BV	SURF
10	DENMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DelC
11	ASSOCIACAO BIP4DAB	BIP4DAB

12	TURUN AMMATTIKORKEAKOULOU OY	TURKU
13	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU
14	PNED GIE	PNED
15	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL
16	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	ECRIN
17	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	IT4I@VSB
18	VIB VZW	VIB
18.1	SCIENSANO	Sciensano
19	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA
19.1	TARKI ALAPITVANY	TARKI
19.2	<i>UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX</i>	<i>UESSEX</i>
19.3	GESIS-LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR SOZIALWISSENSCHAFTEN EV	GESIS
20	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	THL
21	FUNDACIO CENTRE DE REGULACIO GENOMICA	CRG
22	NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY	GRNET
23	UNIVERSITAET BIELEFELD	UNIBI
24	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	UU
25	<i>Health Data Research UK</i>	<i>HDR-UK</i>
26	<i>THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER</i>	<i>UNIMAN</i>
27	<i>UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE</i>	<i>UNIVDUN</i>
28	<i>THE UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM</i>	<i>UNOTT</i>
29	<i>UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX</i>	<i>UESSEX</i>

3.3 Project Acronyms

Table 2. Project Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EOSC-ENTRUST	European Open Science Cloud – European Network of TRUSTed Research Environments
EOSC-ENTRUST-Coordination	EOSC-ENTRUST Project Coordination / Management Team
EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB	Project Management Board (Work Package Leaders)
CA	Consortium Agreement - Agreement concluded amongst EOSC-ENTRUST beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement
Consortium	The EOSC-ENTRUST Consortium, comprising the named legal entities
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action - Part B
EC	European Commission
GA	Annotated Grant Agreement - The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the EOSC-ENTRUST project
EOSC-ENTRUST-GA	EOSC-ENTRUST-General Assembly - all project participants. Corresponds with the Consortium
IC	Indirect Costs
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
PuC	Purchase Costs
PM	Project Manager
PMs	Person Months

Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement
QA	Quality Assurance
SLEAB	Scientific, Legal and Ethics Advisory Board
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

3.4 Project Summary

The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a European network of trusted research environments for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. Countries and institutions have made significant investments in secure and trusted data environments to meet the need for research and policy-driven analysis of sensitive datasets such as people's health and socio-economic status, the habitats of vulnerable species and geo-spatial locations of protected sites.

There are now a large number of such secure environments in operation - linked to national centres, individual organisations or specific research communities. This fragmented landscape poses challenges for both users and providers: researchers are faced with many different systems and access procedures; providers need to manage federated access across multiple, potentially incompatible, technology and governance frameworks.

EOSC-ENTRUST brings together providers of operational Trusted Research Environments from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language. This blueprint for interoperability is anchored in the EOSC Interoperability Framework spanning the four dimensions of Legal, Organisational, Technical and Semantic interoperability.

EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects covering Genomics, Clinical trials, Social science, and public-private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows. Targeted outreach activities will expand this open network with further providers and develop policy papers and guidelines for the full range of stakeholders to create a long-term operational TRE framework within the European Open Science Cloud.

3.5 Project scope and work structure

EOSC-ENTRUST will be implemented through seven work packages, each split into an annual sub-work package to take advantage of the lump-sum approach. This section gives a brief overview of the work packages for orientation.

Figure 1. Interrelationship between work packages.

WP1-2-3: Coordination & Alignment will fulfil three roles:

(1) project management and oversight of compliance with the rules and principles of the project (2) oversight of the interaction between Drivers, Providers and Architecture and on this basis selection or rejection of chosen technical development pathways and (3) connection to the wider European context of Horizon Europe Work Plans, ESFRI priorities and shared interests, and the European Data Spaces including EOSC and the EHDS.

WP Leads: Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR Hub), Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub)

WP4-5-6: Communication

Will ensure that there is cross-work package communication and visibility of outcomes and organising major outreach events. This activity will develop consistent communication and messaging for TREs to use in policy conversations with their national funders, and the promotion of the EOSC-ENTRUST approach among research communities.

WP Leads: Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub), Paola Quattroni (HDR-UK)

WP7-8-9: Drivers (TRE Driver Forum)

Through this WP the project will validate the architecture by adopting its use in the design of trans-national solutions for a variety of domains and governance contexts, including molecular health research, clinical trials data re-use, social sciences, and public-private partnerships.

WP Leads: Jan-Willem Boiten (HEALTH-RI)

WP10-11-12: Providers (TRE Provider Forum)

This WP will connect and coordinate the emergence of TREs across the participating states and beyond. A consolidation of existing public specifications and new standardised presentations of the varied capabilities of these environments will form a comprehensive European resource of the existing approaches, common reference architecture and capabilities for sensitive data research; the development of a best-practice based reference architecture, operating procedures and reference implementations will then be selectively adopted by the TREs by integration into their ongoing continuous improvement plans.

WP Leads: Heidi Laine (EUDAT/CSC), Anssi Kainulainen (EUDAT/CSC)

WP13-14-15: Architecture

Will have overall responsibility for the family of specifications and the base representation and guidelines for the Safe Setting of a generalised TRE.

WP Leads: Pål Sætrum (NTNU), Miikka Kallberg (CSC)

WP16-17-18: Technologies

Will promote and extend specifications for the Safe People (researcher identity and secure identification) and Safe Projects (authorisation of researcher access to specific data sets including data use and data access committee approval processes and technology).

WP Leads: Ludek Matyska (MU), Matej Antol (MU)

WP19-20-21: Workflow processing

Will develop approaches for Safe Data, Safe Outputs and Safe Setting- including the approval of portable workflows, the connection of suitable TRE-HPC capabilities to TRE data environments, and FAIR data flows in and out of the TRE and will look at the specifications from Architecture and Technologies WPs in the context of the EOSC Interoperability Framework, and make recommendations and build demonstrations of the Legal, Organisational, Semantic and Technical interoperability required to allow multiple TRE Providers to work together.

WP Leads: Salvador Capella-Gutiérrez (BSC), Laia Codó (BSC), Philip Quinlan (UNOTT)

Key documents with detailed project information about the activities and tasks of each Work package are to be found in:

- Grant Agreement: Contract between the EC and the beneficiaries establishing the obligations and conditions. An annotated HE version is available here and a detailed EOSC-ENTRUST Description of Action Part A: To be generated once the Grant Agreement is signed. It gathers a project summary, List of beneficiaries, Workplan (Work Packages, Deliverables), Milestones, Risks, Effort in PM, Review meetings.
- EOSC-ENTRUST Description of Action Part B: Excellence, Impact, Implementation, Members of the Consortium, Ethics and Security.
- EC Grant Management Data: Requires login into the EC portal

Note: Documents above are particularly important for new joiners to understand the ambition of the project and the framework in which we have to operate.

4. Project management structure

4.1 Project governing model

EOSC-ENTRUST workflow will be planned and monitored through two main governing bodies: the Management Board and the General Assembly, led by the Project Coordinator. Both bodies will be supported by an independent Scientific, Legal and Ethics Advisory Board, SLEAB.

Figure 2. Governing model of the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

4.2 Project coordination and management

The EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination team will establish effective project governance and internal communication procedures to allow the flow of information within the project. It will also fulfil the administrative tasks associated with the management of the project.

Management of the project is the overall goal of Coordination and Alignment Work Package (WP1-2-3) in the EOSC-ENTRUST Project. This entails overseeing the project execution, ensuring effective and efficient coordination across all activities and participants to deliver the project goals, benefits and expected impact within time, scope and budget and with an adequate level of quality. WP1-2-3 specific objectives are:

1. Ensuring EOSC-ENTRUST meets its objectives and work plan with high-quality guidelines
2. Overall administrative and financial project management for a successful achievement of project goals
3. Defining and implementation of communication procedures within the project and with external stakeholders, including the EC and review preparation
4. Establish a project governance structure
5. Performing ethical and legal analysis
6. Strategic alignment with the EOSC Partnership and projects, the EHDS, and projects funded under the HLTH-2022-IND-13-02 and INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06 calls, establishing contacts and regular communications.
7. Investigate and plan exploitation as a route to sustainability, in close collaboration with WP2A.

4.3 Description of roles and responsibilities

4.3.1 Project Coordinator

Table 3. Project Coordinator details

Name	Peter Maccallum
Organisation	ELIXIR Hub
Email	peter.maccallum@elixir-europe.org
Role	<p>ELIXIR Hub is appointed as Coordinator</p> <p>The Coordinator is and shall be a central point of contact between the Beneficiaries and the EC in particular regarding the management of the Grant.</p> <p>Specific duties: Legal responsibility for a contract, budget oversight and control, submission of deliverables and milestones to EC, chair of GA and PMB. The Coordinator is supported by the Project Management Team in regards to the financial and contractual administration of the project.</p>

4.3.2 Project Management Team

The Project Management team will be led by the ELIXIR Project Management Office and leverage their experience and processes for managing large, international consortia to ensure timely delivery and effective communication and collaboration across WPs, and towards internal and external stakeholders.

Table 4. EOSC-ENTRUST Project Management Team

Team	Maria Tyler, Maria Dolores Fernandez
Organisation	ELIXIR Hub
Email	EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org
Role	<p>The project management team is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, providing the necessary project management support to deliver the project.</p> <p>In particular, the project management team is responsible for the following tasks and activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● implementation of all management and organisational tasks ● scheduling of decisions ● monitoring the achievement of set milestones ● timely submission of deliverables ● organisation and documentation of the meetings of the Project Bodies ● dissemination of all relevant information and action items across the Consortium ● accounting for all financial aspects of the Project and ensuring timely submission of all required reports to the EC.

The project management team will support and report on the execution of the project work plan and budget utilisation, providing the mechanism to identify and manage project risks and opportunities.

Communication dynamics will be promoted across the project, keeping the right level of engagement among stakeholders. Slack and Google Drive will be collaboration tools used from the first stages of the EOSC-ENTRUST project. These tools will guarantee the means for efficient communication within the Consortium, fulfilling internal communication needs.

Meetings

The EOSC-ENTRUST project management team meets on a weekly basis.

4.3.3 Work Package Leaders

EOSC-ENTRUST Work Package Leads are responsible for overseeing the technical progress of the project and ensuring interoperability and alignment of co-dependent tasks across work packages. They are also responsible for presenting the work carried out by the WP to the European Commission and for the content of their WP activities within the periodic reports.

WPLs are responsible for the proper execution of the DoA and the implementation of the decisions of the EOSC-ENTRUST Management Board (EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB). The WPLs collectively make up the PMB. They are expected to identify issues, risks and opportunities within the technical tasks of the EOSC-ENTRUST Project and take appropriate actions to ensure the project delivers the anticipated benefits both at the work package and project level. Risks or opportunities that cut across more than one work package should, together with a suggested action, be elevated to the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB during the monthly meetings. The WPLs, as the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB and via the Coordinator, report on the project progress to the EOSC-ENTRUST-GA at least every 12 months.

WPLs are responsible for filtering project information from the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB meetings to their work packages via their dedicated WP distribution lists, during their regular meetings, or via other communication means they deem fit, e.g. Slack. WPLs are responsible for scheduling their own WP meetings, creating and circulating an agenda, and taking and disseminating minutes.

In the case of beneficiaries not performing their roles, WPLs are expected to promptly document the situation and raise it with the EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination in order to swiftly address reputational or technical risk for the consortium.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, each WP is co-led by two leading institutions. Both leads are expected to attend the PMB meetings, but where a WPL is unable to attend and her/his deputy neither, it will be accepted that one co-lead attends. In specific cases, they may deputise to a predefined Deputy Work Package Leader.

Contact: eosc-entrust-pmb@elixir-europe.org

For more information, please refer to the ELIXIR Hub document Work Package Leader's Good Practice Guide².

4.3.4 Task Leaders

Each Work Package is broken down into tasks and sub-tasks. Each Task Lead is responsible for prompt and on-time performance and fulfilment of the assigned task and subtask as per

² ELIXIR Hub document Work Package Leader's Good Practice Guide: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jZAhcO4wYMsm8pdd22vO7wNai0wg83H7Fm_R08EL_FQ/e/dit#heading=h.d7m9lv9j5el8 [accessed 15.03.2024]

the Description of Action (DoA) in cooperation with all task participants and liaising with the respective WPL.

The Task Leads must ensure that the fulfilment of their task activities is accomplished in due time in line with the commitments identified in the DoA.

Task Leads shall promptly notify the WPL of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the completion of the assigned task. Each participant must ensure timely contribution to the allocated tasks, as requested by each Task lead and/or WPLs. Any encountered issue should be discussed with the Task Lead and, if needed, escalate to the WPL level.

The designated task leaders are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5. EOSC-ENTRUST Task Leaders

Task #	Organisation
T1.1	ELIXIR
T1.2	EUDAT
T1.3	ELIXIR
T2.1	ELIXIR
T2.2	CSC
T2.3	ELIXIR
T4.1	ELIXIR
T4.2	HDR-UK
T5.1	CSC
T5.2	HDR-UK
T6.1	CSC
T6.2	ELIXIR
T6.3	HDR-UK
T10.1	CSC
T10.2	Sigma2
T11.1	BSC
T11.2	CSC
T12.1	CSC
T12.2	DelC

T12.3	Sigma2
T13.1	CSC
T13.2	CSC
T14.1	CSC & UiB
T14.2	CSC & UiB
T14.3	CSC & UiB
T15.1	CSC & UiB
T15.2	CSC & UiB
T16.1	CSC
T16.2	MU
T16.3	MU
T16.4	GRNET
T17.1	MU
T17.2	CSC
T17.3	GRNET
T18.1	MU
T18.2	MU
T19.1	BSC
T19.2	BSC
T20.1	BSC
T20.2	BSC
T21.1	BSC
T21.2	BSC

This list will be updated accordingly and kept in this live version of the Handbook, stored in the project Google Drive.

4.4 Decision-making and advisory bodies

4.4.1 General Assembly (EOSC-ENTRUST-GA)

The General Assembly (EOSC-ENTRUST-GA) is the ultimate decision-making body and it is composed of representatives of all project Beneficiaries. The EOSC-ENTRUST-GA will be informed of the project progress in a timely manner (Management Board meeting minutes circulated to all partners). The EOSC-ENTRUST-GA shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum). *If the quorum is not reached at a meeting, decisions should be taken by correspondence as specified in Clause 6.2.2.8 of the Consortium Agreement.*

If necessary, each Beneficiary shall also be entitled to nominate a replacement Representative in the event that the original Representative is unable to attend any scheduled meetings of the EOSC-ENTRUST-GA.

Meetings

The EOSC-ENTRUST-GA will meet once a year to be updated on the project progress and plans.

The Coordinator - or his deputy - shall chair the General Assembly. The Chairperson of the General Assembly shall:

- be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the General Assembly; and
- chair meetings of the General Assembly.

Where the Chairperson of the General Assembly cannot attend a General Assembly meeting, the General Assembly shall nominate a replacement to chair the meeting for the purposes of such meeting of the General Assembly only, provided that the replacement must be a Representative. Such replacement shall be deemed Chairperson of the General Assembly.

See Section 6 of the Consortium Agreement for further information regarding the General Assembly.

Table 6. EOSC-ENTRUST General Assembly members.

Participant	EOSC-ENTRUST GA Member
ELIXIR / EBI-EMBL	Peter Maccallum, Jonathan Tedds
CSC	Susanna Repo, Miikka Kallberg
BSC	Salvador Capella-Gutiérrez, Laia Codó
EUDAT	Anssi Kainulainen, Heidi Laine

HEALTH-RI	Jan-Willem Boiten, Anne van der Kant
MU	Ludek Matyska, Matej Antol
SIGMA2	Gunnar Boe, Abdulrahman Azab
UiB	Pål Sætrum, Sushma Grellscheid
SURF	Mark van de Sanden, John van den Berge
DeIC	
BIP4DAB	Mariana de Freitas
TURKU	Anne-Marie Tuikka, Mari Tauriainen
UTARTU	
PNED	Wei Gu, Christophe Trefois
UL	Brane Leskošek, Polonca Ferk
ECRIN	Maria Panagiotopoulou
IT4I@VSB	Jan Martinovic
VIB	Frederik Coppens
CESSDA	Alen Vodopijevc
THL	Persephone Doupi
CRG	Jordi Rambla
GRNET	Themis Zamani
UNIBI	Alexander Sczyrba
UU	
HDR-UK	Paola Quattroni

UNIMAN	Carole Goble
UNIVDUN	
UNOTT	Nawar Ismum
UESSEX	Beate Lichwardt

4.4.2 Management Board

The EOSC-ENTRUST Management Board (EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB) is composed of the Project Coordinator, Project Manager and of EOSC-ENTRUST Work Package Leaders. It is responsible for ensuring alignment and coordination across Work Packages and for the successful execution of the project.

The EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB shall be responsible for the overall execution of the Action, the quality of the action, alignment across all Work Packages, and, in line with the Consortium Agreement, decision-making and the initial finding of amicable solutions for any disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action. The EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB will ensure the smooth operation of the Action and guarantee that all efforts are focused towards the Action Objectives, Deliverables and Milestones. This will be achieved by regular monthly meetings and thorough reviews of progress reports. It will also ensure that all Beneficiaries are regularly updated on scientific progress.

EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB members shall have named deputies to ensure proper representation in all meetings. The Management Board will be supported by the EOSC-ENTRUST-Coordination.

Table 7. EOSC-ENTRUST Management Board members

Role	EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB Member
Project Coordinator	Peter Maccalum (ELIXIR Hub)
WP1-2-3 Leader	Peter Maccalum (ELIXIR Hub)
WP4-5-6 Leader	Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub)
WP7-8-9 Leader	Jan-Willem Boiten (HEALTH-RI)
WP10-11-12 Leader	Heidi Laine (EUDAT)
WP13-14-15 Leader	Pål Sætrum (CSC)

WP16-17-18 Leader	Ludek Matyska (MU)
WP19-20-21 Leader	Salvador Capella-Gutiérrez (BSC)

Table 8. EOSC-ENTRUST Management Board Deputies

Role	Management Board Deputy
Project Coordinator	Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub)
WP1-2-3 Leader	Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR Hub)
WP4-5-6 Leader	Paola Quattroni (HDR-UK)
WP7-8-9 Leader	Anne van der Kant (HEALTH-RI)
WP10-11-12 Leader	Anssi Kainulainen (EUDAT/CSC)
WP13-14-15 Leader	Miikka Kallberg (CSC)
WP16-17-18 Leader	Matej Antol (MU)
WP19-20-21 Leader	Laia Codó (BSC)

4.4.4 SLEAB (Scientific, Legal and Ethics Advisory Board)

EOSC-ENTRUST will make use of the Scientific, Legal and Ethics Advisory Board (SLEAB) for progress review and external advice. The SLEAB will provide recommendations for the scientific strategy of this project. The SLEAB includes independent experts in life science areas, ethics, infectious diseases and economy, whose backgrounds cover science and industry.

Meetings

The SLEAB meets at least once a year or ad hoc by request of the EOSC-ENTRUST-Coordination or the PMB. They provide direct feedback to the PMB.

Section 6 of the Consortium Agreement contains further information about the SLEAB.

Contact: EOSC-ENTRUST-SAB@elixir-europe.org

4.4.4 Meetings with the EC Project Officer

The EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination will coordinate meetings with the EC Project Officer upon need and when requested by this representative of the European Commission.

There are two official meetings that will tentatively take place at month 18 and 36, the Mid-Term review and Final review meetings.

4.4.5 Summary of meetings

Table 10. EOSC-ENTRUST meetings chart.

Meeting	Period	How	Goal
Meetings with PO + EC Internal Experts	Every 6 months or less.	Video conference Content to be defined with PO. Attendance: EC, Coordination, WPLs when needed Owner: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination	Project monitoring
EOSC-ENTRUST-GA (General Assembly)	Yearly	Content to be defined by EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB. Attendance: All beneficiaries Owner: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination	Informing and reflecting on the work done and future steps.
EOSC-ENTRUST-PM B (WP Leaders)	Monthly TC, first Monday of the month	Video conference or F2F collocated with other meetings Owner: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination	EOSC-ENTRUST WP alignment.
SLEAB (Scientific, Legal and Ethics Advisory Board)	At least once a year (GA) or by request	TC or collocated with PMB/ GA meetings. Attendance: SLEAB, Coordination, PMB	Independent advice.

		Owner: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination	
Bilateral meetings	When requested	Attendance: WP leader Owner: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination	Align and implement EOSC-ENTRUST DoA with WPs activities
WP regular meetings	Monthly or according to WPs plan	According to WP needs Owner: WP Leaders	Organisation of work plan and tasks.
EOSC-ENTRUST-Co ordination meetings	Monthly	Attendance: Coordination team Owner: Project Manager	Align and implement EOSC-ENTRUST.
Regular review meetings	M18 and M36	F2F in EC premises. Attendance: PO, EC and external experts, coordinator and WP leaders Owner: EC	Assess project performance.

4.5 Communications management

The communications management process determines how to communicate most efficiently and effectively to the various stakeholders. It defines and documents the communication items content, format, frequency, the audience and expected results. It also defines how to communicate project status and the assignment of activities to the various stakeholders, and the communication strategy for each stakeholder, based on their interests, expectations and influence in the project.

The EOSC-ENTRUST communication strategy is a formal project deliverable that is due in M6 (August 2024) D4.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan.

Once this deliverable is submitted, it will be linked to this Project Handbook.

4.5.1 Internal Communications Plan

The EOSC-ENTRUST Consortium will adopt the following approach to communications:

- Use of electronic mail as the main tool for communication within the consortium.
- Slack³ is available for instant messaging, sharing and VC. Group communication channels were created by EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination.
- Documentation of discussions, agreements and decisions made by phone is encouraged. Specifically, video or phone conferences should always have an agenda and minutes, which should be made available through the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive⁴ and in the appropriate folder.
- Several distribution lists have been initially created which can be used by any participant depending on the subject of the message. Additional lists may be created as the project evolves, if necessary. The EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination team will be responsible for updating the below-mentioned lists with the information received from participants. When a list is used, care should be taken by participants to use the “reply to all” feature only when relevant. The table below shows the distribution lists created by the time of publishing this deliverable.

Table 11. Mail distribution lists.

Distribution list	Description
EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org	EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination team
EOSC-ENTRUST-all@elixir-europe.org	All project participants signed up to EOSC-ENTRUST mailing lists
EOSC-ENTRUST-admin@elixir-europe.org	EOSC-ENTRUST admin contacts + Coordination team
EOSC-ENTRUST-GA@elixir-europe.org	
EOSC-ENTRUST-legal@elixir-europe.org	EOSC-ENTRUST Legal contacts + Coordination team
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Coordination-Alignment@elixir-europe.org	WP1-2-3, leads and members

³ If you need access to Slack, please contact eosc-entrust-coordination@elixir-europe.org

⁴ If you need access to the project Google Drive, please contact eosc-entrust-coordination@elixir-europe.org

EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Communication@elixir-europe.org	WP4-5-6, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Drivers@elixir-europe.org	WP7-8-9, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Providers@elixir-europe.org	WP10-11-12, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Architecture@elixir-europe.org	WP13-14-15, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Technologies@elixir-europe.org	WP16-17-18, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-WP-Workflow-Processing@elixir-europe.org	WP19-20-21, leads and members
EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB@elixir-europe.org	EOSC-ENTRUST project management board + Coordination team
EOSC-ENTRUST-SAB@elixir-europe.org	EOSC-ENTRUST Scientific, Ethics and Legal Advisory Board + Coordination team

4.5.2 Email guidelines

Good practice when using email is essential.

1. Project related mails should be tagged with project short name “EOSC-ENTRUST” and also indicate when action is required (ACTION REQUIRED, FEEDBACK REQUIRED). Subject of the email should be added.
2. Participants must respond promptly to any email received. When that is not possible, at least acknowledgement of receipt of all messages is strongly recommended, especially when answering an explicit request.
3. Carefully consider whether “reply to all” is required.
4. When individual messages between participants are exchanged, use of the same tag is strongly encouraged (e.g. EOSC-ENTRUST: WPL meeting_agenda).
5. Messages need to be concise but clear, especially when requests are made.
6. Message text should include the content needed for the recipient to action the requests.
7. Deadlines must be made explicit.
8. No relevant issues for the work to be performed should remain unclear.
9. When feasible avoid sending emails out of working hours or indicate a reply is not expected outside of working hours.

4.5.3 Dissemination

Dissemination is an important activity for all EC projects, which requires that the scientific work and its results are made openly available, as early as possible and in a form that is easily accessible, understandable and reusable⁵.

WP4-5-6 “Communication, Dissemination & Outreach” oversees communications, dissemination and exploitation and will submit Deliverable 4.1 with all specific actions related to communicating, disseminating and exploitation opportunities of the EOSC-ENTRUST project results.

The EC also provides an enriched approach to communication and dissemination in Horizon Europe research and innovation for project participants⁶

5. Project Reporting

5.1 Deliverables

5.1.1 Who generates project deliverables?

As official results of the project, deliverables deserve special attention and are generated and reviewed according to specific procedures. As a rule, the generation of deliverables is a responsibility of the corresponding work package lead beneficiary and the process will be supervised by the corresponding WPL. The lead beneficiary will be responsible for drafting the deliverable and gathering contributions from work package participants as appropriate. Prior to submission to the EC, deliverables will undergo an internal review process that is detailed below.

5.1.2 Deliverable structure, guidance and tips

Project deliverables are to be submitted at specific times that will be stated in the DoA and as of the date of the submission of this deliverable, are detailed in the Participant’s Portal.

Note: The “expected delivery date” listed in the DoA always refers to the last date of any month. e.g. ‘June 2024’ means ‘30th June 2024’ / ‘Feb 2025’ means ‘28th Feb 2025’.

Deliverables reflect the results achieved during the lifetime of the project, and they are important documents to assess the progress achieved.

⁵ EC’s Open Science policy:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>

Each deliverable must use the deliverable template prepared by the EOSC-ENTRUST Communications Team that can be found in the Templates folder on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive⁷.

The name of the Deliverables and Milestones should be written in the following format:

- EOSC-ENTRUST_Dx.x - Name of the deliverable
- EOSC-ENTRUST_Mx.x - Name of the milestone

The template has six predefined sections, that can be adapted depending on the nature of the deliverable:

- Executive Summary (Max ½ page, should provide an overview of the work carried out and the conclusion)
- Contribution Towards Project Objectives (indicate with Yes/No if the deliverable contributes to the key result)
- Introduction (1-1 ½ pages, describe deliverable scope and the methodology to be applied)
- Description of Work Accomplished (Describe what has been done. Interactions with other WPs? Collaboration with external partners/projects? Dissemination activities carried out?)
- Results (Present and discuss the results obtained)
- Conclusion
- Impact (Present and discuss the impact obtained)
- Next Steps
- Deviation from Description of Action (If applicable, describe the deviation from the Description of Action and the justification and plans to avoid this deviation impacting the work plan)

5.1.3 Deliverable review process

5.1.3.1 Review for quality

The review process must use the following quality criteria as reference.

As regards to content:

- **Completeness:** Information must address all aspects related to the purpose for which the information is produced. On the other hand, redundancy of information must be avoided, as it obscures the clarity of documents.
 - *Related indicators:* Missing content, Redundancy.
- **Accuracy:** Information contained in the document must be reliable and must correspond with reality. This means that all background information used in the reports should be appropriately supported by references. Foreground information

⁷ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1wKpmeACdUk-QLmw_QDgg-3wn1tt6fUxr?usp=sharing

should be sufficiently supported so that misinterpretation is avoided. Use of statistically validated objective data is to be prioritised.

- o *Related indicators:* Error, Insufficient references/objective supporting data, Ambiguity.
- **Relevance:** Information used in the document should be focused on the key issues and be written in a fashion that takes into consideration its target audience.
 - o *Related indicators:* Irrelevant information.
- **Depth:** all information used should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.
 - o *Related indicators:* Lacking detail, Excessive detail.

As regards to appearance and structure:

- **Adherence to standards:** it is important that deliverables are prepared with uniform appearance and structure so that, even if they are produced by different authors, they appear as originating from a single initiative.
 - o *Related indicators:* Lack of uniformity in presentation.

5.1.3.2 The review process

Within the EOSC-ENTRUST project, the review process shall be coordinated by the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination.

- A. As and when a deliverable approaches due, it will appear in the monthly project monitoring spreadsheet⁸ three months prior to the submission deadline. A link to the deliverable template will be provided, as well as guidelines for producing the document.
- B. If the WPL themselves will not be drafting the deliverable, it is their responsibility to forward the request to the appropriate WP member(s), who will be undertaking the task of drafting the deliverable (the deliverable authors).
- C. The Deliverable Lead must nominate a minimum of two reviewers. Before informing the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination of who the reviewers will be they should seek agreement from the nominated reviewers. The reviewers should ideally be from a different WP and have a thorough understanding of the deliverable topic so they can provide sufficient technical critique/review. If it is deemed that the review by someone with additional expertise is required, e.g. such as a case where a deliverable has a focus on ethical or regulatory/legal issues, members of any of the Advisory Boards of the EOSC-ENTRUST project may also be asked to be a reviewer.
- D. The deliverable author(s) should work on their deliverable within their Work Package folder on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive.

⁸ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/151r4cTwTfi0nGnijwdVCAInRaF4-mCpNvGBzyRSjRsPs/edit#gid=1091470126>

- E. Where more than one person is producing the deliverable, the lead deliverable author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.
- F. If the WPL(s) do not draft the report themselves, once the first draft of the document is produced by the author(s), they will be expected to have the WPLs review it to assess the content from a scientific/technical perspective.
- G. Reviewers will be expected to check the deliverable against the quality criteria described in section 5.1.3.1. above. Any suggested edits or comments should be made within the Google Doc which allows for a collaborative working environment. The deliverable author(s) must then proceed with the amendments or comments on the reviewed document.
- H. 1.5 weeks prior to the deliverable due date, the final draft of the document should be submitted to the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination, by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive.
- I. The EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will distribute the link to the PMB for a final review, allowing the PMB seven (7) days to review it. Once approved, the EOSC-ENTRUST (on behalf of the Project Coordinator) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and submit the final document to the EC via the Participant Portal.
- J. In addition, the EOSC-ENTRUST will upload all public deliverable reports to Zenodo and notify the Consortium. The final document will also be available on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive in the Deliverables and Milestones folder⁹.

During the whole process, it is recommended that there is one responsible author that acts on behalf of all authors and communicates with them for evolving the document.

5.1.3.3 Illustrative timelines

1. Three months prior to the due date, the deliverable will appear in the monthly project monitoring report with a link to the pre-prepared deliverable template.
2. Two months (60 days) prior to the due date, author(s) identify the reviewers and inform the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination.
 - 2.a If multiple people will be producing the deliverable, the lead author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.
 - 2.b Author(s) produce the first draft of the deliverable report.
 - 2.c If the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the deliverable report.
3. 1 month (30 days) prior to the due date, the author(s) must send the draft report to the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive. The EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will review

⁹ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1S-V6p8PyJbVuyU5Eof3DH9MsZdsE2Fzs?usp=drive_link

the draft for formatting before forwarding it to the pre-identified reviewers, allowing them two weeks to provide comments directly within the Google Doc.

3.a Reviewers' input is gathered within the Google Doc using suggested edits and comments.

3.b Author(s) generate a revised version of the document taking on board the suggestions and comments of the reviewers.

4. 1.5 weeks (10 days) prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive. The EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the PMB (all WPLs) and the GA (Countries) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to review the document. The OG are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc.
5. Three days prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination with the consolidated, final version.
6. The Coordinator (or the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload the final version in the Participant Portal and to Zenodo.
7. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Submitted' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP1, RP2, RP3) in the 04. Deliverables and Milestones folder¹⁰ on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive.

Note: Although the illustrative timeline starts three months prior to the due date with drafting beginning two months prior to it, this process can begin earlier if the authors wish, and deliverables can be submitted ahead of schedule.

In case of time constraints, an exceptional streamlined procedure for the deliverables may apply upon agreement with the PMB.

¹⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1S-V6p8PyJbVuyU5Eof3DH9MsZdsE2Fzs>

A tracker with the deliverable due dates is available on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive¹¹.

5.1.4 List of Deliverable Authors

The most up-to-date list of Deliverable Authors list is available on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive and the Participant's Portal.

5.2 Milestones

Each milestone must use a clean copy of the milestone template and must not exceed one slide. It is the responsibility of the Milestone Lead organisation to produce the milestone report or to deputise the responsibility to someone else upon their agreement.

5.2.1 Illustrative timelines

1. 3 months prior to the due date, the milestone will appear in the monthly project monitoring report with a link to the pre-prepared milestone template
2. 1.5 months (45 days) prior to the due date, if the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the milestone before submitting it.
3. 1.5 weeks (10 days) prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the EOSC-ENTRUST-Coordination by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive. The EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the PMB (all WPLs) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to provide any comment. The PMB are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc however, this shouldn't be a time consuming process for the PMB.
4. Three days prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination with the final version.
5. The Coordinator (or the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload it in the Participant Portal.
6. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Submitted' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP1, RP2, RP3) in the 04. Deliverables and Milestones folder on EOSC-ENTRUST¹².

¹¹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/151r4cTwTfi0nGnjwdVCAInRaF4-mCpNvGBzyRSiRsPs/edit#gid=1091470126>

¹² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1S-V6p8PyJbVuyU5Eof3DH9MsZdsE2Fzs>

- the answers to the ‘questionnaire’, covering issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact, notably in the context of the EC and the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and EC and the Horizon Europe monitoring requirements.

Each partner shall send or provide within the technical report template, as requested, information about the work performed and efforts devoted in the corresponding period to the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination, within 30 calendar days after the end of the reporting period. Effort figures can however be requested by the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination at any point during the project. For the purpose of accountability, beneficiaries are requested to keep track of their efforts at the task/activity level. This facilitates the linkage between effort and progress when reporting to the EC.

5.3.2 Lump Sum Reporting

***Disclaimer:** Beneficiaries must always ensure they follow the EC financial reporting guidelines. The details provided here are valid at the date of the document submission but may be superseded by changes to EC rules. See the Lump Sum Reporting Guidelines available on the ONLINE Manual on EC Participant Portal¹⁴ for further information.*

EOSC-ENTRUST project has been awarded under the EC Lump Sum Grants. Lump sum grants are grants where the grant amount is fixed and will be paid out if the project is implemented as set out in the DoA. Lump sum funding follows, wherever possible, the standard rules and processes for actual cost grants which imply a maximum 100% of the costs reimbursed for eligible project activities. There is no reporting of actual costs or of resources.

EC funding for Lump Sum Grants is paid in several instalments and follows the standard schedule: a pre-financing payment (80% for EOSC-ENTRUST), additional pre-financing payments (in some grant schemes), interim payments at the end of each reporting period (up to a maximum of 95%), and a final payment of the remainder of the balance including the 5% Guarantee Fund.

Interim payments pay the lump sum shares for work packages completed during the corresponding reporting period and accepted by the Project Officer. There is no possibility for interim payment of partially completed work packages. The Lump Sum contribution breakdown per beneficiary per WP is available in the DoA.

When agreed by the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB, lump sum contributions can be adjusted by transfers of amounts between beneficiaries during the project life. This may not require an

14

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=8913115>

amendment, if the action is implemented as described in DoA. Other parts and aspects of the lump sum grant agreement can be amended in the same way as for actual cost grants; however work packages that have already been completed and paid cannot be amended.

5.3.2.1 Declaring WPs complete

In lump sum grants the ‘status of work packages’ table in the Grant Management System is required to be completed. Work packages will be marked as ‘completed’ or ‘not completed’. On the basis of the status of the work packages and the amounts of lump sum shares attributed to each beneficiary in the grant agreement, the consolidated financial statement will be automatically generated for all beneficiaries. Certificates on financial statements are not used in lump sum grants.

Unlike for actual cost grants there is no contractual obligation to keep financial records for the projects.

6. Project Processes

6.1 Risk management

6.1.1 Risk identification and categorization

An initial list of key project risks has been identified during the preparation of the Action and a respective table of identified risks is in the Participant’s Portal, as a new procedure under Horizon Europe. All beneficiaries are asked to screen their activities with regards to additional new risks and to promptly notify the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination of any significant new risk(s) having the potential to affect the completion of the assigned WP.

6.1.2 Risk assessment, registry and action plan

The EOSC-ENTRUST coordination will add any new risks, including a description of the possible impact, to the risk register (EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring¹⁵ and EC Portal) and bring any additional risk(s) to the attention of the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB.

Prioritisation of the risks will be based on the possible impact (I) and the probability (II) of realisation of the risk. Based on the prioritisation appropriate mitigation activities and/or contingency plans will be developed.

¹⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/151r4cTwTfj0nGnjwdVCAInRaF4-mCpNvGBzyRSjRsPs>

A mitigation plan for each identified risk has to be developed by the concerned work package and the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination and presented to the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB as part of the risk management process. The list of identified risks are part of the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool.

6.1.3 Risk monitoring

The risk register will be reviewed by the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination on a monthly basis informing the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB of any significant change when it happens or at least every six months in the regular meetings. WPLs and Task leads are asked to actively contribute to this activity which will be overseen by the Project Coordinator and EOSC-ENTRUST coordination.

An update of the risk assessment activity, including the major risks identified with their corresponding mitigation and contingency plans, will be included in the Periodic Report to be submitted to the European Commission. Newly identified risks will be communicated to the EC via the EC project continuous monitoring tool (requires EC login).

The EOSC-ENTRUST coordination will drive the risk management process, dealing with the identification, assessment and follow-up of threats and opportunities likely to affect the project performance as a whole.

Concrete actions arising from the analysis of the risks will be included in the project monitoring tool and distributed to participants and WP involved on a monthly basis via the automatic report generated and distributed by the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool.

For any questions contact EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

6.2 Issue management

The project issue management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, prioritising, assigning, resolving and controlling issues. It is a four step process that the Project Management Team executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

1. **Issue Identification:** Issues can be identified by any project stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, using different communication channels such as meetings and emails (EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org). The issues are registered in the Issue Log.
2. **Issue Assessment and Action Recommendation:** a first informal assessment by the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination, considers the category, impact, urgency of the issue, followed by a more detailed analysis to identify

the root cause and recommend a solution. This information is documented in the Issues Log tab in the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool and used as input to the appropriate decision makers (based on the escalation process). The decision is also documented in the Issues Log.

3. **Actions Implementation:** After issues are evaluated and the remediation actions approved, the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will incorporate these actions into the appropriate project related documentation such as the Change Log tab in the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring.
4. **Issue Control:** During the regular EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB meetings the status of the issues related actions incorporated into the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring, will be revised, and new issues identified.

Concrete actions arising from the analysis of the issues will be included in the project monitoring tool and distributed to participants and WP involved on a monthly basis via the automatic report generated and distributed by the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool.

For any questions contact: EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org

6.3 Project change management

The project change management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, approving, prioritising, planning and controlling changes, and communicating them to all relevant stakeholders. It is a five step process that the Project Management Team executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

1. **Change Identification:** a request for a change can be submitted formally via an email to the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination (EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org), or can be identified and raised during meetings as a result of decisions, issues or risks. The requested change should then be captured in the Change Log section of the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool including information to identify the change, such as the requestor, a short description, identification date, etc.
2. **Change Assessment and Action Recommendation:** the size and impact of the change on the project scope, schedule, cost, quality, risk, and other project boundaries is assessed, whereafter a recommended action will be documented by EOSC-ENTRUST in the Change Log section of the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool.
3. **Change Approval:** the approval of a project change will be determined by the

type and impact of the change requested and in line with best practice in EC grant. For low impact change requests which do not require formal approval by the EC, the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will advise who must approve the change, be it EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination, the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB or the EOSC-ENTRUST-GA. If a formal change to the Grant Agreement is required then the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination will use the information provided in the Change Log as an input to the formal amendment request that will be submitted to the EC after the approval of the GA or the EOSC-ENTRUST-GA depending on the type of the change.

Only when a significant change is requested or a number of smaller requests have been received, will an amendment request be submitted to the EC.

4. Change Implementation: the activities related to the implementation of approved changes will be documented by the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination in close collaboration with the EC.
5. Change Control: new or open changes will be identified/reassessed by the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination, using the Change Log section of the EOSC-ENTRUST Project Monitoring tool and will be brought to the attention of the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB, the EOSC-ENTRUST-GA or the GA in due course.

For any questions contact EOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

6.4 Quality management

The implementation and execution of EOSC-ENTRUST follows the principles of Horizon 2020 and European Commission rules and are more specifically defined in the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action and in the Consortium Agreement provisions. The procedures described in this section shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium or with the EC, or any of the EC guidelines for project implementation. The project will be managed according to EC best practice with a dedicated communications effort.

EOSC-ENTRUST will explore the establishment and operation of a suite of high-quality communications channels, periodic project monitoring including work plan execution, quality assurance, data management, use of resources, innovation management activities, and risks.

EOSC-ENTRUST quality objectives are to:

- Ensure that all the project related activities and deliverables are fulfilling the scientific and technical quality expectations and are following available quality and compliance standards issued by the EC under the Horizon Europe funding

scheme¹⁶.

- To define the processes and assets to be utilised by all consortium partners to meet these objectives and to provide support to partners to achieve the required quality and to monitor adherence to the standards set for the project, in alignment with the DoA.
- Ensure compliance with agreed Horizon Europe and EC rules, applicable law and regulations, incl. but not limited to data privacy, handling of funds and ethics. To promote gender equality in the project and science and society issues related to the research activities conducted within the project will be also addressed, looking for suitable guidelines.

6.4.1 Quality policy

The generic quality policy adopted by EOSC-ENTRUST builds upon the following set of principles:

- Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project;
- Criteria and standards by which the quality of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production will be identified;
- Description of the tools, methods and techniques to be employed in order to ensure quality will be shared among participants;
- Provisions must be made for monitoring quality during the process and recording compliance and deviation.

Taking into consideration the overall quality policy, quality standards are to be applied to all the work undertaken throughout the project.

6.4.2 Project quality control

The overall quality control of the project results includes the coordination of quality review for all project outputs prior to their submission to the EC.

It is crucial for the project to ensure that deliverables, as official results of the project, are reviewed and checked for quality. This may also apply to other outcomes of the project that are addressed to parties external to the project.

The present document is focusing only on the general methods implemented to ensure quality of written materials delivered to the EC and other partners external to the

¹⁶https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-op en-calls/horizon-europe_en

Consortium. A document produced in a project generally aims to provide information concerning the work, its progress or the derived results. Each document should thus be carefully drafted with rich content, a clear structure and a professional presentation. The three basic aspects for building quality into project documents are content, appearance and timing. It is generally accepted that the relative importance of each document varies, and it is important that overzealous quality criteria do not compromise timing if marginal benefit to the project is minimal.

For more information about the process, see section [5.1.3. Deliverable review process](#).

6.5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The outcomes and impact of the project in relation to the call text will be assessed against Key Performance Indicators. A full list of the KPIs as identified in the proposal can be viewed in the shared folder.

These KPIs can easily be monitored, from the project onset and will be refined in WP6. Progress against these KPIs must be reported to the governance boards, to inform project planning and management, looking forwards (rather than post-hoc assessment), ensuring corrective actions are taken as and when they are needed. Some of these indicators already form part of ELIXIR's suite of indicators, which are used to monitor the infrastructure's performance (mostly internally-facing) and impact (mostly externally-facing), in line with ESFRI's current work on ensuring that the infrastructures it has recognised are adequately monitored.

6.6 Data management plan

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be defined and updated throughout the project lifecycle as part of Task 1.1 and Task 1B.1. The initial version of the DMP must be created by ELIXIR Hub in the first six months of the project within WP1 (D1.2) according to the project scope and the EC requirements.

Any questions regarding the DMP should be directed to the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination team (EOSC-ENTRUST-Coordination@elixir-europe.org).

6.7 Internal conflict resolution and escalation

Conflicts are situations in which one or both parties perceive a threat. They are considered to be critical issues and can be raised by any of the project stakeholders. The Project Management Team should proactively identify, log and raise such issues for resolution.

In the event that an internal conflict arises at a given time, the project coordination and the management structure is formulated to support a bottom-up approach with respect to its resolution.

- Conflicts amongst beneficiaries in any given activity should be discussed at the Work Package (WP) level with the help of the respective Work Package Leaders (WPLs).
- If unresolved, the issue will escalate to the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination that will then use mediation to objectively aim to solve the issue involving all parties affected.
- If unresolved and when the issue is significant enough, the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination could then make a proposal :

- To the EOSC-ENTRUST- PMB if the issue has very limited operation impact and can be resolved at this level. If it is a strategic issue, to amicably resolve the issue.
- To the EOSC-ENTRUST General Assembly if it is a non-strategic issue

At all stages, beneficiaries can reach out to the EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination in case they feel a request has not been adequately dealt with.

7. Configuration management

7.1 Storage of project management artefacts

Project repository

The Project Management Team has created a structured EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive to store the project management artefacts following the same folder convention per sub-folder.

Table 12. Project repository structure.

Top Level Folders	Relevant Content
Project Master Files	<p>Master file with details from the project: contact lists, effort distribution, lists of deliverables & milestones, GANTT chart etc</p> <p>Project monitoring spreadsheet: contains details of all actions, events, deliverables and milestones, along with due dates and templates - monthly reports are generated from this for all partners/WPs.</p> <p>Communication registration form responses: It includes the email address of the partners' participants that are relevant for the monitoring and control activities: PIs, Deputies, administrative, financial and legal contacts.</p>
Legal Documents	<p>Legal documents pertaining to the project: Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, Description of Action, amendments,</p>

	contracts, etc.
WPs	Working folders for the WPs.
Deliverables & Milestones	Repository for project deliverables and milestones (templates, working drafts and submitted documents).
Project meetings, events & TCs	Details of all project meetings and events (agendas, minutes slide presentations etc).
Periodic reporting	Financial and periodic reports from all project partners
Guidance and templates	Project handbook, containing guidance pertaining to all aspects of the project (processes, communications, management structure and responsibilities, etc). Project templates: deliverables, milestones, agendas, minutes, slide presentations, etc.
Project Communications and Outreach Materials	Project branding & style guidelines, press releases, articles, presentations, newsletters, etc.
Grant Agreement Preparation	Working documents for the preparation of the grant agreement.

For any assistance with creating new folders, please contact
EOOSC-ENTRUST-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

Utilisation of project repository is covered in [7.4 File Exchange and Repository](#)

7.2 Naming convention of project management artefacts

The latest version of a detailed, controlled Documents Version Policy outlining the project naming conventions and other configuration management guidance will be included in D1.1 Data Management Plan (M6-August 2024).

7.3 Versioning of project management artefacts

All project management artefacts are under version control.

7.4 File Exchange and Repository

7.4.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Repository

A Google Drive has been created for EOSC-ENTRUST to be used as a repository of relevant information and files which facilitates the exchange of documents within the consortium (i.e. meeting minutes, documents in progress, final versions and other relevant reports or announcements). The EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive also provides a calendar of meetings and events, upload of files, and tracking of important milestones and events at both the project and Work Package level.

- All beneficiaries have been enabled access to the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive once they have signed up to the mailing lists. Access can be granted after filling in the registration form¹⁷.
- The latest version of the EOSC-ENTRUST contact list is uploaded on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive, in the EOSC-ENTRUST list. The up-to-date participants' contact information with clear information of who is included in every mailing list mentioned above will be based on the periodic updates by each of the Work Package Leaders.
- The use of de facto standards based on Google Docs for electronic document exchange among participants is required when possible. PDF format can alternatively be used to avoid excessive size of files when no editing is required. EOSC-ENTRUST uses Google Drive as a project management tool that is simultaneously used as a document management system. The EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive provides a place to store, secure and organise the consortium documentation which helps to ultimately control the quality of documents and conformity of processes.

The tool has capabilities available to set permissions on a file or folder. These clear access rights can be rapidly degraded or defeated entirely by the system admin (coordinator) of the consortium. Users with proper visibility rights and access permission can fuel quality control of the project.

Additionally, a document version history is an efficient way to track who has edited files and when. This platform allows users to revert to an earlier version if the file becomes corrupted or if errors are introduced.

With the notification feature available, each person with permission can invite other consortium participants on document edits and to track changes to a document stored in a shared folder simultaneously.

¹⁷ <https://forms.gle/TYDgRqJbWqFR7RAf8>

EOSC-ENTRUST uses Google Drive to manage quality of the documents and processes by enhancing the centralization of digital assets, promote maintenance of quality and support backup and data protection.

Any publication in EOSC-ENTRUST is governed by Annex 5 and Article 17 of the Grant Agreement and Article 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement. Scientific Publications and Communication to the public will be covered by the Communication, Dissemination and Outreach WP.

The Documents Versioning Policy outlined in 7.2 is key to clean and consistent archiving; especially towards the mid/end phase of the project when an increasing number of digital outputs and documents are created. Using the same tag for email subjects and for the documentations in attachments, fuels clear communication and leads to reduced email burden and duplication of work.

8. Key legal document

8.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (GA) is the main legal document underpinning the project's execution – effectively, a contract between the beneficiaries and the EC. It is first signed by the EC and the Coordinator. Each beneficiary then accedes to the Grant Agreement by executing an accession form. The Grant Agreement mainly provides information on the grant (parties, duration, start date, budget, etc.), obligations of the Beneficiaries towards the EC (such as reporting requirements), as well as the intellectual property framework and other legal conditions. The Grant Agreement is dated 1st March 2024 and has the GA Number 101131056

The Grant Agreement core document includes a standard text describing the general rules and regulations governing EC projects, including financial rules (e.g. which costs are acceptable, how payments are handled, etc.), Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) (who owns the results, how access to such results is enabled, etc.) and other general conditions applicable to EC projects. These generic provisions can be supplemented (but not contravened) with project-specific provisions via a Consortium Agreement (see below), which enables projects to set out their specific IPR detailed rules, governance mechanisms, etc.

Beyond its core terms and conditions, mostly standard text, the Grant Agreement also includes the following annexes, which form an integral part of the contract:

8.1.1 Annex 1. Description of the action (DoA)

The most extensive and important Annex to the Grant Agreement is the Description of Action (DoA), which comprises the technical description of the work to be undertaken in the project (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones), the description and roles of the different partners, allocated effort in person-months, and budget details. The DoA is derived from the original proposal submitted to the EC for evaluation and approval, and it is the benchmark against which project progress will be judged. Compared to the rest of the Grant Agreement and annexes, which are mostly model texts, the DoA is specific for each project. It is important to remember that the DoA is an integral part of the Grant Agreement, and therefore it is a contractual commitment of all Beneficiaries.

8.1.2 Annex 2. Estimated Budget (Lump Sum Breakdown) for the action

This Annex refers to the overall budget for the EOSC-ENTRUST Project and includes the Lump Sum Breakdown for all project beneficiaries. This document is automatically generated by the EC Participant Portal.

8.1.3 Annex 3. Accession form of beneficiaries

This form is required to be signed by all the project beneficiaries to formally accede to the EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement. If a new beneficiary joins the project, this form will be requested to be signed by the new institution joining the project.

8.1.4 Annex 4. Model for the financial statement

This form refers to the summary of costs to be reported by those partners receiving EC funding for each reporting period.

8.1.5 Annex 5. Specific rules for carrying out the action

The beneficiaries must implement the action as described in Annex 1 and in compliance with the provisions of the Agreement, the call conditions and all legal obligations under applicable EU, international and national law. Section 2 of the Model Grant Agreement specifies the content of this annex.

The signed Grant Agreement and its annexes will be available on the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive¹⁸ once finalised

¹⁸ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1uIoq5nsU8KQ7wtfh1_GnuQHcuyiZAbGA?usp=drive_link

8.1.6 Changes to the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed whenever any important project parameter changes: partnership, project duration, budget, etc. Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called ‘Grant Agreement amendment’. Most changes that trigger Grant Agreement amendments relate to updates in the Description of Action (DoA) (e.g. changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, changes in partner’s teams, budget transfers across Beneficiaries, etc.). These can be relatively minor, in which case they tend to be grouped and implemented together in one go, or major, which might trigger an amendment on their own, especially if it is urgent that the change is officially entered into the contract.

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the EC by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be aware of and approve any proposed changes before the amendment is requested.

The EOSC-ENTRUST coordination will be responsible for following-up on amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project.

The procedure is as follows:

1. The Project Management team will keep track of all needed amendments. Meetings and communications with the beneficiaries affected will enable the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination to compile all the necessary information to support the changes.
2. The list of modifications will be circulated to the General Assembly for their information and approval.
3. The EOSC-ENTRUST coordination will prepare the following documentation:
 - a. A new version of the DoA with the modifications in track changes.
 - b. A first version of a “Request Letter” to be sent to the EC Project Officer including the changes.
 - c. Other documents needed to request modifications.
4. The EOSC-ENTRUST coordination will circulate an amended version of the DoA to the Management Board for validation. The approval by the EOSC-ENTRUST-PMB will be required for any Amendment to the Grant Agreement.
5. As a final step the Coordinator, supported by the EOSC-ENTRUST coordination, will submit on behalf of the Consortium, the Request Letter, the new version of the DoA and all the additional documentation required by EC for the changes submitted.
6. Once approved, the new version of the DoA will also be accessible in the EOSC-ENTRUST Google Drive in the appropriate amendment folder.

The Grant Agreement may be affected by other types of minor changes which do not constitute an amendment, but which must be communicated to the consortium or to the EC through an information procedure. In any case, beneficiaries should contact the

EOSC-ENTRUST coordination to confirm the procedure to follow for any modification needed.

For more information about the procedure, review the updated version of the Online Manual for funding and tenders¹⁹.

9. Ethical considerations

The Ethics and regulatory compliance approach of EOSC-ENTRUST is based on existing national structures: the participating TREs are all nationally regulated via respective competent authorities with established procedures for project acceptance, monitoring and reporting. Any deployment of new technology will be validated through the existing national guidelines. The Driver projects are based on existing, on-going studies with approval for data analysis in place. The use of sensitive or restricted data in the driver projects will not be for additional analysis (requiring new approval) but rather to benchmark proposed solutions against current approaches.

WP1 will be in charge of gathering an independent group of experts for the creation of the Scientific, Legal, and Ethics Advisory Board (SLEAB). This board will ensure that data sharing through the EOSC-ENTRUST platform respects the basic ethical principles.

More details about the EOSC-ENTRUST ethical approach will be part of D1.2 in its Data Management Plan.

¹⁹ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online%2BManual>